

ON THE RESEARCH CONDUCTED IN TOLLISOY

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In 2011, a major archaeological search was carried out by the Uzbekistan–American archaeological team. The main purpose of this joint research was to study the ecology, chronology, historical topography and cultural landscape of the mountain herders living in the foothills of the Molguzar, located on the territory of the Jizzakh region. Modern technologies and new methods are used in archaeological research in Tollisoy valley. In particular, the northern slopes of the Malguzar mountains are designated as areas with limited possibilities for farming due to their poor soil, rocky terrain and aridity, using the distance-advance search method, the edges with a slope of less than 45° are marked, and the search distance is reduced, during the field searches, searches were conducted in flat areas with a width of 25 meters to 1 km [Frachetti, Maksudov: 195–212].

50 archaeological monuments were discovered on the northern slopes of the Molguzar mountain range during the archaeological field survey. Among the monuments found, the population's residence was more than the graves. The ancient inhabitants were found to have lived in a dense state.

The expedition, which began as a continuation of research in 2011, gained a number of innovations. Unlike previous studies, the researches of 2023 were carried out in a relatively small area, that is, in Karatash Valley, Besharchasay valley, and Galchasay valley, starting from the northern slopes of Molguzar and flowing to Tollisoy valley. Initially all streams were re-surveyed, resulting in the discovery of a number of relics that had not been identified in previous searches. A total of 40 monuments were identified in Karatash Valley, Besharchasay valley, and Galchasay valley. (previous survey had identified 28 of these three streams)

There are several comments on the toponymy of Tolly village, where the research was conducted. According to Q. Hakimov, the name of the village is related to a willow tree. Willow trees growing on the edge of the springs were distinguished from other trees by their scarcity and attracted people's attention, therefore, it served as a symbol in the name of the village. At first it was called Tollikishlak, later the word kishlak was dropped and it was called Tolly [Q.Hakimov: 97]. During our conversation with the villagers, we came across the idea that the meaning of the name of the village is “a village located on a hill”. When looking at the sources, this idea was proven to be close to the truth. The root of Tolli may be derived from the Arabic word tal-Hill. The names of villages located in different places of Uzbekistan, such as Tali Barzu (Hill near Samarkand; "high hill", Arabic tal-hill, Sugd barz or "Barzu Hill"), Talliyo‘lgon (hill walker), Tallak(tal-hill, ak- diminutive affix), Tallaktov, Tallak Oysara (from the local names of mount Ko‘hitang, tal-hill, ak- diminutive affix), prove this idea [S.Qoraev: 118–119].

Another of the achievements during our research in 2023 was the rock carvings. There are about 100 carvings on 28 rocks from the Botatash and Yamonkhistov streams. The stream where the rock is located is in the eastern part of the village, approximately 500 meters away from the village, 50-60 meters above the stream. Their coordinates and height above the water level were determined. These found rock carvings were given a conditional name. This conditional name is called Tolly because it is found in the streams around Tolly village. Almost all the pictures are drawn in the range of 5, 10 cm, and the most common in the images correspond to mountain goats. It can be seen that the ancient artist observed mountain goats a lot. In addition, these

images are similar to mountain goats found in other regions of our republic, sometimes with single, and in most cases with double horns, long neck, handsome body, two or four legs and short tail [J.Kabirov: 19]. Additional, it is possible to find scorpions, deer, various geometrical images and other symbols in the images. Among the photos there is also an image of people in a group. It can be seen from the general scene that two people are depicted facing each other as if they are fighting, and the others are watching around them, it can also be an image of a ceremony. All humans have a human penis enlarged and shown separately from the legs. This style is more characteristic of the Early Iron or Early Middle Ages.

On the hill between the Botatash and Yamonkhistov streams, at an altitude of 1255 m above sea level, a rectangular grave surrounded by cut mountain stones was discovered (Fig. 1). Such types of graves are related to the Karakol culture, which is the most common among the 3 types of graves included in this culture [V.Kubarev:28]. Similar graves were found by Toshboyev near the village of Jelli Gulli in the Jizzakh region and were opened and studied [F. Toshboev: 55–59]. There is no stone slab on the found grave, most likely it was taken away by people. Due to the lack of excavation, it is difficult to give a clear opinion about the chronological period.

Houses are complexly located in the Karatash 3 object, and we identified 12 traces of houses that are visible to the eye. A small area of 4*3 size has been marked for excavation, in the center of the marked area, according to our estimate, there is an intersection of the foundation of the rooms. During the excavation, foundations built using mountain stones were discovered, and it can be seen from the traces that the upper part of the foundation and the wall fell to the outside (east). 40 cm was dug down, traces of the wall were clearly visible, and interestingly, during the excavation, no pottery fragments were found from the excavation site (Fig. 2). Due to lack of time, it did not go down to the mainland and the place was restored. Such stone foundations are also found in the monuments on the slopes of the Molguzar mountain range.

In conclusion, it can be said that the foothills of Molguzar were considered to be a land of special importance in the history of nomadic herders of Central Asia. The migration of nomadic pastoralists to the mountainous Ushrusana region was observed from the 2nd millennium BC to the 15th century [F. Maksudov: 12]. It can be said that one of the main factors for the arrival and settlement of ancient herders in Ushrusana was the convenience of the mountainous areas for cattle breeding and the wide green pastures on the slopes. Archaeological achievements in recent years prove this. The news obtained during the 2023 research shows that more research is still needed in the area.

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Illustrations

Fig. 1

Fig. 2